

The Role of Spiritual Culture in the Development of Moral-Spiritual and Combat Competence of Future Officers on the Basis of an Integrative Approach

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Abstract: This article examines the need to develop moral, mental, and combat competence as an important area of professional competence for future officers in accordance with the new requirements of science, technology, and production in the process of globalization.

Keywords: New Uzbekistan, motherland, fidelity, spirituality, culture, morals, military activity.

INTRODUCTION

Special attention is being paid to the practice of modernizing the world education system based on the competence approach, improving the methodological foundations of teaching in accordance with modern development trends.

Ensuring harmonization of future officers with social, economic, psychological knowledge in daily activities, improving the ability to effectively apply pedagogical and psychological knowledge in daily activities, improving the system of military education. Integrating socio-humanitarian and general professional and general sciences with the solution of modern wars in the world and world levels is of particular relief.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The radical improvement of the quality of competitive specialists is becoming the quality of training on the basis of reforming the system of higher military education, providing national and professional requirements to international standards. Therefore, it is necessary to develop mental and war competence as an important area of the professional competence of the future officers in accordance with the new requirements of science, technology and production. According to the action strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it has identified important tasks, such as improving the quality and efficiency of higher military educational institutions. This requires the improvement of the pedagogical and psychological system of moral and obligatory competencies in future officers in the Integrative Approaching, on the basis of modern war development.

In new Uzbek army, special attention is paid to radically reforming the system of future officers, and future officers mastered modern knowledge, spiritually mature people, to grow spiritually, to have faithfulness in the Motherland in the heart of military personnel. Priorities for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan are identified in further improvement. In the implementation of these priorities, important regulations have been adopted to further develop military education in our country, ensuring its effective operation. "Our Armed Forces need to be more interested in educating the fighting, soldiers and officers, and - the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev. [1]

A number of researches are being carried out on the development of innovative and pedagogical models of content to develop the spiritual and cultural institutions of the higher military educational institution in the process of establishing the technology of higher military educational institutions. Especially through the modification of acceptable diagnostic tools, improving professional pedagogical and spiritual and creativity is important in improving the skills of the cadets, knowing the skills of the cadets, and enforcing the skills of professional, etc. At the same time, it is important to improve the educational opportunities of spiritual education and the harmony of spiritual and universal values in the development of social intelligence of higher military educational institutions and the harmony of spiritual and universal values.

It should be noted that through the integration of the spiritual and moral and mentally, mentally educational capabilities of servicemen, they are considered as a priority to the development of military pedagogical mechanisms for the formation of spiritual and moral qualities. As a result, the need is becoming one of the necessary tasks for the formation of qualities such as loyalty, combat activity, discipline, courage, self-sacrifice, courage, durability, and spiritual qualities. In this regard, the important factor of educating the military personnel who will protect the border border border guards, and increase spiritual integrity, are an important factor in social development. Improving the activities of military administrative sectors in the new Defense Document in the types of troops and allows the combat preparation of the armed forces and the development of the country's defense capabilities to the development of professional culture. PF-6022 on January 28, 2022 the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Development Strategy for New Uzbekistan" No. PF-4947 "Further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", 2017 PF-506 on May 19, 2017 Organizations of interethnic relations and friendship with foreign countries, 2010 Deadlines for measures, 2018 "On measures to radically reform the state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan". In the works of the decisions of the Republic of Uzbekistan ensuring the fact that the works of the work of the Works of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the necessary improvement of the spiritual and educational level of the military and enforcement of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan" On the necessary and educational level of the military personnel of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Resolution of the Republic of Uzbekistan The ideas of the demonstration of the demand for the development of improved influence of the national army of the Republic of Kazakhstan shows that it is important to raise spiritual culture in the cadets, the further improvement of combat readiness, improvement of moral and mental training.

"Holy of the Motherland is an honorable duty to protect him! "The idea of Ez'u is of emphasis in raising social activism, high patronymic, spiritual culture and national spirit of servicemen and strengthening the country's defense capacity. What is spiritual culture and what concepts does it?

Culture is a set of material, spiritual resources created by people in the process of nature, divisions, and modification of these riches and ways of restoration and style of these riches.

The term "Culture" is characterized in colorful meanings in modern scientific literature. According to the terms "Culture" and "Culturt", the Latin meant the meaning of the "processing", "maintaining". It was later used in the context of "to be enlightenment", "Be" educated ".Therefore, there are three main layers of culture: 1) regular mimic and physical active work of humanity;2) development, consumption and conservation of material and spiritual benefits;3) values, moral concepts, territorial societies that apply to life. Culture is an active creative activity. Man develops and progress through active creativity. Creativity - man expands the boundaries of spiritual spiritual activities. Man will only have creativity status through creative skills, mental and physical labor. [2]

The base culture is the level of development of various abilities, which appears as a democratic, aesthetic, moral, national, psychological, local, regional, labor, and communication culture. It represents the ability to live in environmental conditions and reflect the culture of society. Society culture includes national values, knowledge, aesthetic mind, of human activities, and their results, cultural relations, specifics in human fair activities. Culture reflects the level of development of society, which develops with material and spiritual production, social and interaction, politics, family, morality, services, services, services, services, services, services, services, services. [3]

The foundation of childhood for culture and through education and training is systematically diligated and improved.

A civilized person is a great man, who understands something, and understands others, is a good spirituality of the cultural person. This is the case of a cultural person, it is free from aggression, a set of personal unrest. This is Man needs to form a higher education institution. [4]

In our opinion, the spiritual and cultural quality is to reflect the spiritual qualities of the prospective officer, to be used in daily and professional, religious, religious, religious, religious, religious, religious, religious, religious, religious, hypothesis, analysis, assessment, and negative effects.is the ability to distinguish.

The spiritual culture of the future officer covers a complex structure, containing a system of spiritual and moral knowledge, spiritual quality, professional and cultural values, moral, combat training.

In improving the spiritual and cultural qualities, it is necessary to justify the following principles:

- Concentific approach - understand future officers biological and psychic, social and spiritual, understanding, and self-awareness, rational and irrational unity;
- View that the need to pedagogical support for future officers is a person who senses an individual; In this case, respect for high social values in the development of human personality, respect for each caduscity and unique; His social rights and freedoms recognizable;
- Purpose, object, proficiency, effectiveness indicators and results manifest in cadites; view future officers as the main entity in this process; In educational activities, depending on the main functions of ethnic and regional, cultural, socio-economic, socio-economic conditions, socio-economic conditions, taking into account the individual participants individual, A stratified approach selected by the content, forms and techniques of educational work. [5]

The principle of harmony with nature requires compliance with the following rules:

- 1) study and nurse of the individual and personal characteristics of the cadet;

- 2) rely on cateaching and needs;
- 3) ensuring the interaction of psychological and pedagogical diagnosis, consulting and correction;

The principle of culture with culture is to create a future self-development and self-change, to create culture, cultural events, cultural events, and cultural emergencies, which are created - cultural events. Treating as cultural officers as a cultural and educational space, the educational process is understood by relying on national traditions, tradition, ceremonies. [6]

Conclusion

In a humane way to organize the relationship in the educational process - respect between teachers and future officers, to listen carefully to them, to be treated good and focusing on them, the needy person is defended, necessary, important, to feel; Lensial to create psychological tenses for the comprehensive interaction of teachers and cadets, as well as to create a valuable manner in all respects, in future waiters, to educate their personal opinions in the upcoming official, socius.

In short, it is desirable to analyze the principles of the globalization process to increase the need for modern social development, the need to increase the spiritual and cultural responsibilities of the future.

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